

MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS AND SYMPTOM CLUSTERING

Akbarova M. Kh.

(associate professor, margubaakbarova66@gmail.ru , TUIT),

Dzhangazova K.A.

(assistant, qumrinisod@mail.ru , TUIT),

Nurdullaev A. N.

(assistant, Alishernurdullaev@gmail.com, TUIT),

Nabiev N.I.

(graduate student , nadirbeknabiev98@gmail.com , TUIT)

**Tashkent University of Information technologies named by Muhammad al- Khorazmi,
Uzbekistan**

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Abstract: The thesis titled "Machine Learning Algorithms and Symptom Classification" delves into the critical intersection of machine learning algorithms and medical diagnostics through symptom classification. Symptoms serve as vital indicators in diagnosing medical conditions, and the integration of machine learning algorithms enhances the precision of symptom classification. This thesis aims to explore the application of machine learning algorithms in symptom classification within the medical field, examining their effectiveness and potential implications for clinical practice. By analyzing the integration of machine learning algorithms into symptom classification, this study seeks to contribute to the advancement of diagnostic methodologies and healthcare practices.

Keywords: Machine Learning Algorithms, Symptom Classification, Medical Diagnostics, Integration Precision, Effectiveness, Potential Implications, Clinical Practice, Diagnostic Methodologies, Healthcare Practices

Introduction

Symptoms, clinical in practice critical to importance have is a diagnosis and treatment processes in understanding and in defining main characters as works Machine learning algorithms and symptoms in clustering more efficient approach for critical important have to the topic about access part of machine learning algorithms medicine in the field symptom in clustering important role and their in practice application emphasizes.

Main Part:

Objectives: "Machine Learning Algorithms and Symptom "Clustering". important scientific problems learning and medicine in the field importance analysis to do the goal does main purpose, machine learning algorithms using symptom of clustering medicine in the field role learning and analysis is to do

- Machine learning algorithms and their medicine in the field symptom in clustering how application
- Machine learning algorithms and clinical of medicine classification processes effect
- Machine learning algorithms medicine in the field in practice symptom in clustering himself check.
- Machine learning algorithms medicine in the field symptom in clustering mutually to compare with how integration.
- Machine learning algorithms medicine in the field symptom in clustering prospects.

This is the thesis own including machine learning algorithms and medicine in the field symptom of clustering data of analysis integration own into takes. This is the analysis based on medicine in the field critical topics and problems is recognized and to them development for help will give.

This is the goal done increase for the following tasks marked:

Machine learning algorithms and their medicine in the field symptom in clustering how application analysis to do

Machine learning algorithms and clinical of medicine classification processes effect study.

Machine learning algorithms medicine in the field in practice symptom to cluster application as a result himself check.

Machine learning algorithms medicine in the field symptom in clustering prospects and integration study.

Of the thesis results based on machine learning algorithms medicine in the field symptom in clustering mutually to compare with how integration about recommendations to give. Machine Learning Algorithms and Symptom Clustering Study : Machine learning algorithms , medicine in the field symptom in clustering critical important have has been from technologies is one It's fast main purpose, machine learning algorithms using symptom of clustering medicine in the field role is learning .

Algorithm Analysis and Classification: Machine learning algorithms analysis and their clinical in practice classification to the topic about important from tasks is one of the thesis main duties, this algorithms medicine in the field symptom in clustering how application and their in practice effect analysis is to do. Clinical In practice Himself Check: Machine learning algorithms symptom in clustering himself check and the results present reach to the topic about again one important is a task. This is the thesis of algorithms medicine in the field in practice symptom in clustering how results take exit to learn the goal does. Integration and Prospects: Thesis main purpose of machine learning algorithms medicine in the field symptom to cluster integration and future prospects is learning . This is integration and prospects based on clinical praxis development and medicine in the field practices to improve directed recommendations and approaches offer will be done.

Summary part

This thesis is on "Machine Learning Algorithms and Symptom Classification". important scientific problem and their medicine in the field importance to learn the goal does Machine learning algorithms, medicine in the field symptom in clustering critical important have being came This thesis, machine learning algorithms symptom in clustering himself study , their clinical in practices effect and application analysis does Article, machine learning algorithms medicine in the field symptom to cluster of integration and future prospects about more concept will give . This of research results, clinical practices improve and diagnostic methodologies in development important role own into takes.

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